

ISic1173

Funerary inscription for Sosis

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2018.07.16 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance

In re-use in the external wall to the left of the main entrance of the Chiesa SS. Sacramento, Piazza Duomo

Coordinates

38.039634, 14.022922

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Oratorio del Santissimo Sacramento, Piazza Duomo

Physical Description

A large block of grey limestone, built into the wall of a church. The lower right corner is missing, and the upper middle of the face shows cracking. Only the front face is visible in the current setting.

Dimensions

Height 88 cm

Width 103.5 cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek letters across the upper part of the face; the text fills the width of the stone on both lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat crude, large letters, probably later Hellenistic: sigma has parallel top and bottom strokes; omega is closed, tending to elliptical in form; mu has vertical first and last strokes, mid-point descends half-way only; phi has small circular eye and extended vertical; kappa has short tails; alpha has broken bar; epsilon has short middle stroke

Letter heights:

Line 1: 85 mm

Line 2: 75-80 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 10-15 mm

Text

1. Σώσι Νύμφων
2. Κραφάγε χάρε

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Sosis Nymphon 'the meat-eater', farewell!

Commentary

SEG 37.763 reports the observation of Masson that Κραφάγε should be an epithet, meaning 'eater of meat'. Νύμφων is either the patronymic (in which case the genitive ending has either been omitted, or the right edge of the stone was trimmed for re-use in the church wall), or else a second name in the Sicilian fashion, with Κραφάγε then an additional epithet.

Digital identifiers:

TM 284913

EDR 108737

EDCS 39102327

PHI 140656

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1173. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI

edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351703>

Photo J. Prag